

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS HANDICRAFT PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO RAMANATHAPURAM DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

Handicraft is an art of craft in which people create something solely with their hands or using simple instruments. Handicraft industries are those that manufacture items by hand, rather than utilising machines, to suit the needs of the people in their community. Artistry, crafting, and handcrafting are all names used to describe handicrafts. Handicrafts emerge with the rise of human creative activity.

Keywords- Consumer buying behaviour, Handicraft products, handmade products

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Customer Buying Behaviour refers to the buying behaviour of the ultimate consumer. A firm needs to analyse customer buying behaviour because buyer's reactions to a firm's marketing strategy has a great impact on the firm's success. Buying Behaviour is the decision processes and acts of people involved in buying and using products. Consumer Buying Behaviour refers to the actions taken (both on and offline) by consumers before buying a product or service. This process may include consulting search engines, engaging with social media posts, or a variety of other actions. It is valuable for businesses to understand this process because it helps them better tailor their marketing initiatives to the marketing efforts that have successfully influenced consumers to buy in the past.

1.2 OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To study the customer buying behavior towards handicraft products
- To analyze the customer awareness towards handicraft product
- To identify the expectation and satisfaction of customers towards handicraft product
- To study the reason for the preference of handicraft products
- To find out the different kinds of handicraft product purchased by the customer

1.3 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

When it's comes to customisation, sometimes the customer didn't get what they actually expected and this results in the disappointment of the customer and this will make them not to buy the products from the particular seller any more Products can be expensive since their work is very delicate, so it costs more than the machine made products. Some customer find this difficult to buy the product they like.

1.4 METHODOLOGY

Methodology is an essential aspect of any investigation. It enables the investigators to look at the problems in a systematic meaningful and in an orderly way. The methodology comprises sources of data selection of data and analyzing the data.

Data Collection Method;

There are two types of data collection methods used:

- 1.Primary data collection.
2. Secondary data collection.

Primary Data Collection method;

Primary data is the data in which the researcher collects data through various methods like interviews, surveys, questionnaires etc., to support the secondary data. Primary data collected in this project is using the questionnaire.

Secondary Data Collection Method;

Secondary data is data collected by someone other than the user. Common sources of secondary data for surveys, organizational records and data collected through qualitative methodologies or qualitative research. Secondary data used in this project is records of journals and through the Internet .

1.5 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- Mohsin Shafi, Liu Junrong, Yongzhong Yang, Deng Jian, Imran UR Raahman and Mahdi Moudi (2021): “Factor influencing the consumer acceptance of innovation in handicraft product” The overall results show that most consumers are willing to accept innovation in handicrafts, and various types of innovations positively influence their purchase intention. These types of innovations have not been examined earlier from the consumers perspective in the handicraft sector. Particularly, the findings indicate that consumers prefer authenticity, packaging, and high quality handicraft products. Generally, authenticity and innovation are considered opposite to each other. This paper combines these two contradictory terms to provide a novel approach to enhancing handicraft value to attract consumers.
- Sriparna Guha, Anirban Mandal and Fedric Kujur (2021): “The social media marketing strategies and its implementation in promoting handicraft product: a study with special reference to Eastern India” Handicraft industry is still lagging behind to adopt social media to market their valuable products to their potential customers. They mostly depend on government sponsored trade and fairs to sell their products to their customers in different places of India. The current research work has made an initial attempt to study the probable impact of SMM activities of handicraft products on brand awareness and brand image and these two constructs were put to measure their impact on brand equity and purchase intention Further, the study also measures the influence of brand equity on consumers purchase intention
- Shah and Patel (2016) underline that in-spite of the developments taking place in almost all industry domains in India, besides agriculture, handicraft in India employs a large number or population in rural India. The industrial development in India must be in sync with the development plan for the rural handicraft sector. The development should focus on

individuals as well as communities involved in handicrafts. The e-commerce platform should be explored and exploited for the benefit of the rural handicraft sector.

- Dash .M (2015): The study was to understand the role of family influence in buying behavior towards handicraft products". The studies show that families have a positive and significant influence in buying handicraft. In case of purchasing any handicraft items the purchase itself influences the buying decision most. Family is the most influential group for the consumer. The study revealed that the orientation towards culture and tradition for buyers happened from its parents. And buyer has to do the same orientation for its family member.

1.6 TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS

The tool used in this study to analysis was

- Simple percentage method
- Coefficient of correlation
- Chi square test

ANALYSIS

The present study the researcher has analysed the consumer buying behaviour towards handicraft products product with reference to Kilakarai is relating to personal details such as age, educational status, income expenditure pattern and other related details are analysed with the help of primary data.

1.6.1 GENDER WISE CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS

TABLE 1

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS
1.	MALE	3	6%
2.	FEMALE	47	94%
	TOTAL	50	100%

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION

It is seen from table 1 that, out of the 50 respondents, 94% are female respondents and 6% are male respondents.

It is known that the majority of the respondents are female.

FIGURE 1

1.6.2 AGE WISE CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS

TABLE 2

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO.OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS
1.	BELOW 20	22	44%
2.	20 - 30	25	50%
3.	30 - 40	2	4%
4.	ABOVE 40	1	2%
	TOTAL	50	100 %

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION

From the above table 2, it is clear that, 50% of the respondents belong to the age group of 20 - 30 years, 44% of the respondents are in the age group of below 20 years, 4% of the respondents are in the age group of 30 – 40 years. and 2% of them

belong to the age group of above 40 years. From the analysis it is known that majority of the respondents are in the age group of 20 – 30 years

1.7 CHI –SQUARE TEST HAS BEEN APPLIED TO FIND OUT THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN OCCUPATION AND OPINION ABOUT THE COST OF HANDICRAFT PRODUCTS

Null Hypothesis (H₀)

There is no significant association between occupation and opinion about the cost of handicraft products

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁)

There is a significant association between occupation and opinion about the cost of handicraft products

OPINION & OCCUPATION	VERY EXPENSIVE AS COMPARED TO MACHINE MADE PRODUCTS	BUDGET FRIENDLY	WORTH FOR THE MONEY	VERY CHEAP	TOTAL
WORKER	2	2	-	-	4
SELF EMPLOYED	1	-	-	1	2
HOUSEWIFE	-	1	-	-	1
STUDENT	9	14	15	5	43
TOTAL	12	17	15	6	50

$$R = (O-E)^2 / E$$

$$E = \frac{\text{Total Column no total of respondents} \times \text{row total}}{\text{Total}}$$

$$\text{Degree of Freedom (DOF)} = (R-1) (C-1)$$

Where as

O= Observed Value

E= Expected Value

R= Total number of rows

C= Total number of columns

$E1 = \frac{4*12}{50} = 0.96$	$E5 = \frac{2*12}{50} = 0.48$	$E9 = \frac{1*12}{50} = 0.24$	$E13 = \frac{43*12}{50} = 10.32$
$E2 = \frac{4*17}{50} = 1.36$	$E6 = \frac{2*17}{50} = 0.68$	$E10 = \frac{1*17}{50} = 0.34$	$E14 = \frac{43*17}{50} = 14.62$
$E3 = \frac{4*15}{50} = 1.2$	$E7 = \frac{2*15}{50} = 0.6$	$E11 = \frac{1*15}{50} = 0.3$	$E15 = \frac{43*15}{50} = 12.9$
$E4 = \frac{4*6}{50} = 0.48$	$E8 = \frac{2*6}{50} = 0.24$	$E12 = \frac{1*6}{50} = 0.12$	$E16 = \frac{43*6}{50} = 5.16$

THE TABLE OF EXPECTED FREQUENCY SHALL BE:

0.96	1.36	1.2	0.48	4
0.48	0.68	0.6	0.24	2
0.24	0.34	0.3	0.12	1
10.32	14.62	12.9	5.16	43
12	17	15	6	50

CALCULATION OF CHI - SQUARE

O	E	(O - E)	(O - E)²	(O - E)²/E
2	0.96	1.04	1.08	1.12
2	1.36	0.64	0.41	0.30
0	1.2	1.2	1.44	1.2
0	0.48	0.48	0.23	0.48
1	0.48	0.52	0.27	0.56
0	0.68	0.68	0.46	0.68
0	0.6	0.6	0.36	0.6
1	0.24	0.76	0.58	2.47
0	0.24	0.24	0.06	0.25
1	0.34	0.66	0.43	1.28
0	0.3	0.3	0.09	0.3
0	0.12	0.12	0.014	0.12
9	10.32	1.32	1.74	0.17
14	14.62	0.62	0.38	0.03
15	12.9	2.1	4.41	0.34
5	5.16	0.6	0.36	0.07
			TOTAL	9.94

Chi-Square test = $\sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$

$$= 9.94$$

Degree of freedom $V = (r - 1) \times (c - 1)$

$$= (4 - 1) \times (4 - 1)$$

$$= 3 \times 3$$

$$V = 9$$

For $V = 9$, $(\chi)^2_{0.05} = 16.9$

INTERPRETATION:

The calculated value of Chi-square 9.94 is more than the table value 16.9. Therefore the hypothesis is accepted. Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between the occupation and opinion about the cost of handicraft products by the respondents.

1.8 CORRELATION TABLE**(CALCULATING AGE AND PURPOSE OF THE RESPONDENTS)**

AGE (X)

AGE	BELOW 20	20 - 30 YRS	30 - 40 YRS	ABOVE 40
X	22	25	2	1

PURPOSE (Y)

PURPOSE	DECORATIVE	GIFTS	SELF INTEREST	CREATIVITY
Y	5	12	18	15

CALCULATION:

S.NO	X	X ²	Y	Y ²	XY
1	22	484	5	25	110
2	25	625	12	144	300
3	2	4	18	324	36
4	1	1	15	225	15
N=4	$\sum X=50$	$\sum X^2=1114$	$\sum Y=50$	$\sum Y^2=718$	$\sum XY=461$

$$\begin{aligned}
 r &= \frac{N \sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2}{N} \frac{\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2}{N}}} \\
 &= \frac{4(461) - (50)(50)}{\sqrt{4(1114) - (50)^2 \times 4(718) - (50)^2}} \\
 &= \frac{1844 - 2500}{\sqrt{4456 - 2500 \times 2872 - 2500}} \\
 &= \frac{-656}{\sqrt{1956 \times 372}} = \\
 &= \frac{-656}{\sqrt{727632}} \\
 &= \frac{-656}{853.01} \\
 &= -0.7690
 \end{aligned}$$

INTERPRETATION:

The coefficient of correlation is -0.7690. Hence there is a Negative correlation between age and purpose of purchasing handicraft products

1.9 FINDINGS

- ➤ It is clear that the majority 50% of the respondents are aged between 20-30 years.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 98% of the respondents are UG graduates.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 92% of the respondents are unmarried.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 86% of the respondents are students.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 62% of the respondents have a monthly salary 10,000-20,000.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 96% of the respondents are in favor of using handicraft Products
- ➤ It is found that 56% of the respondents buy handicraft products occasionally
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 82% of the respondents known through social media
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 36% of the respondents are motivated by the manufacturing effort of the seller.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 36% of the respondents intend to purchase handicraft products with their creativity.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 72% of the respondents agree that 60 handicraft products are fashionable,stylish and trendy.

- ➤ It is clear that the majority 30% of the respondents buy handicraft products for its uniqueness.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 32% of the respondents prefer to purchase clay handicraft/pottery.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 34% of the respondents expect quality.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 92% of the respondents are willing to recommend handicraft products. ➤ It is clear that the majority 48% of the respondents are attracted by the promotional activities of buy 1 get 1.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 34% of the respondents considered that handicraft products are budget friendly.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 62% of the respondents get the lasting impact about handicraft products from online advertisement.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 42% of the respondents are using the handicraft products for 6 months. ➤ It is clear that the majority 68% of the respondents are satisfied with the quality of handicraft products.
- ➤ It is clear that the majority 44% of the respondents are facing the problem of lacking availability. ➤ It is clear that the majority 36% of the respondents suggest that the product may be delivered quickly.
- ➤ The chi-square test has been applied to find out whether there is a significant difference between the occupation and opinion about the cost of handicraft products by the respondents. The null hypothesis framed that there is no significant difference between the occupation and opinion about the cost of handicraft products by the respondents. The calculated value of chi-square 9.94 is more than the table value 16.9 . Therefore the hypothesis is accepted. ➤ It was found that there is a negative correlation between age and purpose of purchasing handicraft products.

1.10 SUGGESTIONS

Most respondents have a positive opinion about handicraft products, though several areas need improvement by vendors and service providers. To enhance the industry, advertising efforts should be increased, and products should be made more affordable to build a strong customer base. The quality of handicrafts should match prevailing prices, while discounts and attractive designs can further appeal to consumers. Fair advertising, wider distribution channels, and prompt customization options are also recommended. Addressing unavailability, improving infrastructure and technological support, raising awareness of new trends, and strengthening promotional campaigns are essential for growth. The handicraft industry in India is expected to expand rapidly in the future, contributing significantly to economic development.

1.11 CONCLUSION

The study has been undertaken with an objective to explore the buying behavior of consumers. Buying behavior of handicraft products is an important tool to guide the consumers in purchasing handicraft products. As the consumers are getting more aware about handicraft products and their features, the frequency of handicraft buying behavior will increase. Usage of handicraft products will help them to change their lifestyle . There is a need to educate the people on the usage of handicraft products and on identifying the handicraft attributes of products they use. It will come with drastic change in the world, if all nations will make strict roles because handicraft products are essential to save the world from pollution. From this study it is found that most of the consumers in Kilakarai are aware of handicraft products and there

is a positive attitude and behavior towards handicraft products. But at the same time consumers are concerned with the availability and price of such products.

1.12 REFERENCES

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